

Coexistence in Future Optical Access Networks from an Operator's Perspective (Invited)

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Received XX Month XXXX; revised XX Month, XXXX; accepted XX Month XXXX; posted XX Month XXXX (Doc. ID XXXXX); published XX Month XXXX

In this paper, we address the challenges related to the simultaneous operation of legacy and future network technologies in Passive Optical Networks (PONs) and Point-to-Point (PtP) topologies. We explore the coexistence issues for various user categories, including residential, enterprise, factories, and mobile users. The future access networks will need to accommodate multiple technologies concurrently. Our paper demonstrates how G-PON, XGS-PON, and 50G-PON can coexist on the same Optical Distribution Network (ODN) using triple coexistence Multi-PON Modules. However, there are certain limitations that need to be considered, such as achieving a high optical budget and the associated costs, both in terms of monetary investment and CO2 emissions for technology deployment by operators. Additionally, we emphasize the significance of Optical Line Terminals (OLTs) as crucial network components in the future. OLTs play a central role in supporting the traffic evolution with optimal efficiency in terms of throughput, latency, jitter, and adherence to CO2 emission constraints. Finally, we experimentally demonstrate first assessment of 50G-PON prototype with optical budget reaching 23.9dB. Furthermore, we evaluate the potential limitations regarding coexistence by examining the effects of Stimulated Raman Scattering between the DS of 50G-PON and the US of XGS-PON for the first time with real PON systems.

1. Introduction

Ongoing worldwide deployments of Fiber to the Home/Building/x (FTTx) have been taking place since the mid-2000s. As of 2020, there were 726 million households with fiber-based connections, and this number is expected to grow to approximately 1.2 billion by 2027 [1]. Throughout this period, advancements in fiber access network technologies have continued, progressing from Gigabit capable PON (G-PON – Passive Optical Network) to 10 Gbit/s symmetrical PON (XGS-PON) [2]. These developments have resulted in an average broadband speed of 121 Mbit/s in 2020 and projected to increase to an estimated 844 Mbit/s by 2027 [1]. Since over 80 % of the expenses associated with FTTH are related to installing the passive fiber plant, it is crucial to maintain existing Optical Distribution Networks (ODNs) when upgrading to future PON systems.

Although the number of network terminations may not be as high as for FTTH, the evolution of mobile networks has brought about an interesting market for Fiber to the Antenna (FTTA) deployments. FTTA has been instrumental in driving the advancement of Point-to-Point (PtP) interfaces to accommodate higher data rates. Recently, the ITU-T standard for bidirectional fiber PtP connectivity, known as G.9806, has been updated to support speeds of up to 100 Gbit/s [3].

Both network topologies (PON for FTTH and PtP for FTTA) and applications share the same network shelf equipment known as the Optical Line Terminal (OLT), which is located at the central offices. This means that both the network topologies and services applications rely on the OLT for their connectivity and communication needs and future evolutions. XGS-PON

In this paper, we begin in section 2 by highlighting the significance of Next Generation Central Offices (NGCO) in facilitating the coexistence of PtP and PON topologies. Section 3 delves into the anticipated advancements in PtP technologies and the associated challenges of their

coexistence. Furthermore, Section 4 outlines the existing hurdles in current PONs coexistence, while Section 5 explores the potential for supporting 50G-PON on the same fiber infrastructure. Finally, we present an experimental evaluation of a 50G-PON prototype system in this paper, which demonstrates possible optical budgets of 23.7 dB in DS at 50 Gbit/s and 26.9 dB in US at 25 Gbit/s. We also measure the Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS) possible impact due to coexistence of 50G-PON with XGS-PON. This paper is an extended discussion of [4] with extensive discussion on the key role of the OLT for coexistence and with new experimental assessment of a 50G-PON system with amplification to support high optical budget needed for triple coexistence of PONs.

2. Next generation Central Offices for coexistence of PtP and PON topologies

A- Coexistence of mobile and FTTH network in the OLT

Figure 1: Access segment for FTTH based on PON and for Mobile/business users based on PtP connectivity, all via the OLT

In future fixed access networks, the OLT is the key system for operators to deliver fiber to everywhere services, as depicted in Figure 1. It is the operator’s access network equipment that is designed to aggregate and distribute high-speed data and voice signals over optical fibers. Consequently, they play a crucial role in connecting multiple subscribers to the service provider’s network infrastructure. The OLT supports multiple networks topologies, Point-to-Point (PtP), typically for Fiber to The Enterprise or Fiber to The Antenna, or Point-to-multipoint such as PONs for FTTH or Fiber to the Office (FTTH-like connectivity for Small enterprises). An OLT shelf can host up to 15 PON cards of 16 PON ports each for FTTH and one PtP card of 16 ports for Mobile and Enterprise connectivity through an electrical backplane with switching capabilities about few Tbit/s. Consequently, the OLT is aggregating traffics from thousands of all types of users (residential, small enterprises and mobile cell site) to the fixed backhaul/metro network, via its uplink card which consisted so far of 4x10 Gbit/s SFP+ (10G capable Small Form Pluggables). With the arrival of 5G, the uplink cards are being upgraded to support 2x100 Gbit/s interfaces au format QSFP28.

On the access side of the OLT, motivation and techniques for access technology upgrades are being discussed extensively in ETSI with the F5G and F5G advanced [5,6]. F5G, or Fifth Generation Fiber, will create new possibilities by extensively deploying fiber technology across diverse scenarios and extending its reach to all aspects of life, with the aim of benefiting various industry sectors such as telecom, education, healthcare, finance, energy, transportation, and manufacturing. This expansion of fiber connectivity seeks to provide opportunities and advantages to all verticals within these industries.

In table 1, we present a summary of potential access technologies that could be necessary to facilitate the progression from F5G to F5G advanced. Additionally, we offer initial extrapolations of our perspective on what F6G could entail.

In optical access systems, XG(S)-PON has emerged as the default system to meet the F5G era and is steadily gaining popularity. Moving forward, the deployment of the 50G-PON system is anticipated to start during the F5G advanced phase. F5G advanced aims to deliver linear rates ranging from 10 Gbit/s to 100 Gbit/s in future PONs and PtP interfaces. Furthermore, in terms of future advancements for F6G, the technology that emerges from ongoing discussions within Full Service Access Network (FSAN) regarding very-High-Speed PONs (vHSP) could potentially serve as the reference technology. This progression would pave the way for the development of multi-100 Gbit/s systems [7,8]. If these estimations hold true, access networks might have the capability to support speeds of up to 1 Tbit/s for access networks beyond 2030.

Table 1: Potential evolution of technologies from F4G to F6G

Fixed Network Generation	F4G (ETSI)	F5G (ETSI)	F5G advanced (our estimations)	F6G ? (our estimations)
Reference wave	Megabits	Gigabits	Multi-gigabits	Hundreds gigabits
Reference downstream Bandwidth per user	100-1000Mbps	1-10Gbps	10Gbps-100Gbps	100Gbps-Tbps
Reference Upstream Bandwidth per User	50-500 Mbps	1-10Gbps	10Gbps-100Gbps	100Gbps-Tbps
Reference Services	UHD 4K, video	VR video, Cloud Gaming, Smart City	Industrial IoT, Autonomous Vehicles, Smart Cities	industry 4.0, augmented reality, autonomous transportation, eHealth
Reference Architecture	FTTH / FTTHd	FTTH / FTTR	FTTH / FTTR / FTEverything	Green, Advanced Fiber infrastructure, APN
Access Network Technology Reference	GPON/G.Fast	XGS-PON	50G-PON	>100G-PON- vHS-PON
Technical Specifications Reference	GE PtP G.984.x G.9701 G.986	10GE / 10G-PtP G.9807.x G.9806	10G/25G PtP G.9804.x G.9806 Amd1	100GE – 800GE (PtP) G.vhsp (under discussion) G.9806 Amd3
User network interface reference	FE / GE+ WiFi/WiFi5 (802.11n/802.11ac)	GE / 10G+WiFi6/6E (802.11ax)	10GE / 100GE + WiFi7 (802.11be)	100GE IoT , new WiFi
Specification Timeline	2006 (GPON) 2014 (G.fast)	2017 2022	2023	~2030
Production Timeline (significant volume)	2010 (G-PON, GE), 2016 (G.fast)	2018	2027	>2030

B- OLT Hardware evolution with photonic switching and bypass

Figure 2: Schematic view of the evolution of Next Generation Central Offices proposed in the EU project OCTAPUS with optical switching and photonic bypass at the OLT

To meet the higher and higher demanding bandwidth and latency requirements of future use cases, the IOWN group has introduced a new network architecture called the Open All-Photonics Network (APN) and published the Release 1 architecture document for APN. An APN [9] has

been suggested to achieve reduced latency. The APN concept involves utilizing optical components like optical switches for networking purposes, aiming to eliminate delays caused by electrical packet processing. Also following this trend, the European project OCTAPUS introduces a groundbreaking architecture of NGCO [10], as depicted in Figure 2. This involves advanced technologies that are crucial for the future evolution of OLTs and access networks. The increasing demand for ultra-high-speed access network interfaces, driven firstly by the evolution of mobile networks to 5G and beyond (6G), necessitates the implementation of 50G-PON and 100G-PtP interfaces at the access interfaces (IF). To accommodate the high data rates required by these numerous interfaces, NGCO will enhance switching capacities through the implementation of an Optical Circuit Switching (OCS) for an all-optical backplane and potential enhancements of the OLT total switching capacity. These specific advancements in NGCO will contribute to the innovative architectures envisioned for fixed networks as described in the ecosystem, including the following:

- Development of high-speed access network interfaces tailored for 50G-PON OLTs.
- Implementation of a reconfigurable OLT's backplane that can support OLT bandwidth upgrades up to 50T using an OCS all-optical backplane.
- Integration of ultra-low-energy switching and Express ports, enabling ultra-low latency services with an optical front-end based on a "Wavelength Selective Switch (WSS)-express" technology.
- Reduction of power consumption in OLTs through the utilization of photonic technologies and the implementation of sleep mode scenarios to conserve energy.

The NGCO developed in OCTAPUS project will serve as a facilitator for various enterprise use cases, including indoor RAN deployments in settings like campuses, buildings, subways, and Industry 4.0 environments. It also enables fiber connectivity to machines for industrial automation and fiber connectivity to rooms for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Additionally, OCTAPUS NGCO will enhance network resilience and end-to-end latency through the implementation of a photonic bypass. It promotes convergence between point-to-point multipoint (PtPM) and point-to-point (PtP) markets in the OLT. Furthermore, it could showcase dynamic power-saving capabilities.

C - OLT software evolution with SDN

Also, the evolution of OLTs with Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has brought significant changes to the way OLTs are managed, enabling various advancements such as OLT managers becoming controllers, PON slicing, cooperative configurations, and hardware disaggregation [11]. Here's a brief explanation of each aspect:

- OLT Managers becoming Controllers [12]: Traditionally, OLTs were managed through proprietary management systems, limiting their flexibility and scalability. With the adoption of SDN, the management functions of OLTs are separated from the hardware and implemented in software controllers. These controllers provide a centralized point of control and programmability, allowing for more dynamic and efficient management of the OLTs.
- PON Slicing [13]: SDN-based OLT controllers enable the concept of PON slicing, which involves partitioning a PON into multiple virtual networks or slices. Each slice operates independently and can have different Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, security policies, and resource allocations. PON slicing allows for efficient sharing of

network infrastructure among multiple service providers or different types of services.

- Cooperative Configurations [14]: SDN-enabled OLT controllers facilitate cooperative configurations among multiple OLTs in a network. By centrally controlling and orchestrating OLT functions, the controllers can coordinate the operations of multiple OLTs, allowing for enhanced resource utilization, load balancing, and improved fault tolerance. Cooperative configurations enable more efficient network operation and can lead to better overall performance.
- Hardware Disaggregation [15]: SDN-driven OLT architectures have the potential to lead to hardware disaggregation. Traditionally, OLT hardware has been tightly integrated, with limited flexibility for operators to choose components from different vendors. However, with SDN, the control plane is decoupled from the data plane, enabling the use of generic and programmable hardware for OLTs. This disaggregated approach allows network operators to select and upgrade hardware components independently, promoting interoperability and innovation.

The utilization of these technologies relies on the level of network deployment advancement. In one hand, in the case of greenfield deployment scenarios, the advancement of Cloud-oriented FTTx becomes significant, as it wouldn't necessitate replacing current equipment (OLTs) and the associated Operation Support System (OSS) would need to be developed regardless. In the other hand, in the case of countries with mature FTTH networks, the transition would involve multiple stages due to the existing deployment of equipment and the already developed OSS for the legacy architecture.

During this period, Cloud-oriented technologies will undergo further development, leading to various scenarios that blur the boundaries between network segments and services. This, in turn, will result in an increasing coexistence of services and network topologies within the central offices of the next-generation infrastructure.

3. Impact of PtP interfaces evolution on the coexistence

Fiber connectivity has become the prevalent method for connecting antenna sites, with dedicated fiber connections utilizing PtP connectivity from the site to the aggregation point for macro-cell sectors. For 5G, a PtP card in current FTTH OLTs (also equipped with several PON cards) to share the OLT equipment for aggregation in a central office [16]. Figure 3 illustrates the possible access network for connecting mobile antenna sites to the core network. In the case of 4G, macro-cells were linked to a switch-router for aggregation, but the prevailing trend now is to utilize only the OLT as the aggregation equipment.

Figure 3: Detailed OLT scheme showing PtP connectivity for mobile Antenna sites and FTTE and PON connectivity for FTTH

For 5G, point-to-point networks are dedicated fiber links that connect two network terminations and serve as the primary optical connectivity

method in mobile networks. These networks rely on optical transceivers that are integrated into the Radio Access Network (RAN) equipment. Figure 3 illustrates an example of Point-to-Point links used in the current deployment of 5G backhaul and fronthaul. In this setup, the backhaul links are connected through an OLT PtP card, which can be housed in the same equipment shelf as OLT cards used for fixed business or residential users, such as FTTE or FTTH connections. The OLT PtP cards in applications are currently being upgraded to support 10 Gigabit Ethernet (10 GEth) ports and will soon be advanced to 25 Gigabit Ethernet (25 GEth) ports.

In the case of fronthaul links between Open Distributed Units (O-DUs) and Open-Remote Units (O-RUs), most of these connections remain highly localized at the antenna site. Therefore, O-DUs and O-RUs are equipped with short reach transceivers that support distances of 2 or 10 kilometers, which are suitable for typical FTTA implementations. These fronthaul links will soon carry CPRI10 (25 Gbit/s) or eCPRI, depending on the O-RU technologies and radio configuration deployed to meet the extensive bandwidth requirements imposed by 5G. However, it is important to note that no CPRI interface has been defined for speeds beyond 25 Gbit/s at present, and therefore, outdoor Industrial Temperature (I-Temp) transceivers, capable of operating within a temperature range of -40 to +85 degrees Celsius, are necessary at the antenna site.

The latest standards recommendations from IEEE and ITU-T [3,17] reflect efforts to specify single-fiber PtP interfaces in order to optimize fiber numbering. These standards are designed for transmission speeds of up to 100 Gbit/s, with products already available on the market. It is noteworthy that IEEE and ITU-T are now providing specifications with convergence efforts for single fiber PtP connections above 25 Gbit/s. However, achieving interoperability remains challenging when operators attempt to combine a multitude of transceivers available from different vendors in the market. These transceivers vary in terms of form factors, fiber reach, optical budgets, modulation formats, wavelength pairs, duplex/simplex configurations, energy classes, and Forward Error Correction or Digital Signal Processing implementation, among other factors. Deploying a pair of PtP transceivers across remote sites, within different types of host equipment (switches, routers, OLTs, Radio Access Network equipment, etc.), introduces complex operational rules to prevent pairing issues and necessitates a larger inventory of spare components.

To address this complexity, recent initiatives such as the Mobile Optical Pluggable Alliance (MOPA) and the Memorandum of Understanding among major European operators aim to streamline the transceiver catalog in the context of O-RAN, focusing solely on the most suitable products for specific use cases.

Also, looking ahead to potential advancements, PtP technologies could leverage the capabilities of the PON Management and Control Interface (OMCI), adopting it for enhanced operation and maintenance tools, including inline remote monitoring, PON-ID, dying gasp, inventory and more. As PtP and PON cards are currently deployed within the same OLT shelves, adopting OMCI in PtP would facilitate convergence between PtP and PONs, leading to simplifications in OLT software-defined networking and virtualization efforts.

Finally, the OLT evolution will certainly be mainly driven by these PtP applications that will require first increased performances in terms of bandwidth per services, line rates of interfaces, latency, and jitter coping Time Sensitive Network (TSN) specifications, privileged access path to content servers, etc. As the PtP interfaces coexist with PONs for FTTH and enterprises in the OLT, all access networks' topologies and segments will benefit from these evolutions.

4. Coexistence of G-PON and XGS-PON challenges

As mobile networks advance to their fifth-generation radio technology, they employ separate radio frequencies with reduced bandwidths to mitigate interference with other radio systems. Similarly, fiber access networks utilize an optical wavelength overlay approach to enable the coexistence of multiple generations of PONs.

Figure 4: Coexistence of G-PON and XGS-PON using MPM at OLT and wavelength overlay (including simplified wavelength plan)

Firstly, the coexistence of G-PON and XGS-PON technologies on the same ODN has been made possible through wavelength overlay. The ITU-T has designated distinct spectral bands for the Downstream (DS) and Upstream (US) carriers of each technology, as depicted in Figure 4. However, achieving this coexistence on the ODN requires the introduction of an additional spectral filter. This filter can be implemented as a separate passive Coexistence element (CEX) or integrated into a Bidirectional Optical Sub-Assembly (BOSA) within a Multiple PON Module (MPM) transceiver [18]. The latter approach is commonly used during XGS-PON deployments and MPM modules are available with possible optical budget classes N1 [14-29 dB] and C+ [17-32 dB] and more recently class D [20-35 dB], following standards specifications.

Despite these precautions regarding spectral and insertion losses being covered by standards, some coexistence issues have been identified between G-PON and XGS-PON. The first issue arises from Stimulated Raman Scattering interactions between G-PON and XGS-PON, potentially causing power depletion on the G-PON [19]. The second issue in a coexistence scenario is that ONUs (Optical Network Units) with high Out-Of-Band (OOB) crosstalk levels may result in crosstalk-induced errors in upstream reception at the OLT of another PON system. To mitigate this risk, the ITU-T has proposed the definition of an OOB Power Spectral Density (PSD) mask, which will be included in a revised version of G.9807.1 (Annex BA). Additionally, other methods to facilitate coexistence are described in [20]. Removing coexistence issues, XGS-PON deployment is growing in volume reaching market as high as G-PON one in 2027 [21].

Still, operators are introducing this new technology, with constraints of the legacy fiber infrastructure that can reach optical budgets as high as 35 dB and bearing in mind the great challenge to reduce CO₂ emissions drastically within the next decade.

Figure 5: Projected evolution of CO₂ emission weight according to Orange group's strategic plan

In 2022, consumption of digital technology accounts for nearly 5% of global emissions, and the sector's emissions are rising exponentially. Telecommunication operators like British Telecom, Vodafone Group, Deutsche Telekom, Verizon, and Orange have made significant pledges to decrease their carbon footprint by 2030 and achieve net-zero carbon emissions by 2040 ~ 2045. Figure 5 displays the projected evolution of CO₂ emission weight according to Orange group's strategic plan, encompassing scope 1, 2, and 3 emissions, along with the actual data reported for scopes 1 and 2 between 2015 and 2022. For Orange Group in 2022, scopes 1 and 2 were 1.30 Mt of CO₂, which represents between 10% and 14% of all emissions, including scope 3. The emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) from digital technologies have reached a level of 4% of the global emissions and are steadily increasing at a rate of 9% annually in terms of energy consumption according to [22].

In an end-to-end optical network for FTTH, the optical access network consumes approximately two-thirds of the energy (60% by the ONU and 7% by the OLT) [6]. Nevertheless, by adopting energy-efficient technologies, increasing renewable energy usage, optimizing infrastructure, and embracing lifecycle management principles, operators are striving to reduce their environmental impact and contribute to a greener future. Now, the emission of greenhouse gases has emerged as a critical determinant in deciding whether to invest in new technologies for future networks and digital services.

In the context of fixed access networks, the primary goal for the future deployment of PON, including XGS-PON, is to showcase a reduced carbon footprint using innovative technologies. However, in the case of the OLT, it has been observed that G-PON + XGS-PON MPM combo line cards consume approximately 1.5 times more power than G-PON-only line cards. Moreover, migrating to XGS-PON requires the replacement of the optical modules and the introduction of new Customer Premises Equipment (CPEs) with new BOSA to support higher bit rate transmissions.

To address this challenge, one potential solution is to increase the splitting ratio to 1 to 128 users (or more) per PON. This approach allows for the deployment of XGS-PON while simultaneously demonstrating a reduction in CO₂ emissions by enhanced sharing of the network equipment. This requires higher optical budget classes to be supported by both G-PON and XGS-PON MPM, typically class D (20-35 dB) which is reached with enhanced Tx/Rx implemented in transceivers [2, 24].

5. Coexistence of G-PON with XGS-PON and 50G-PON

Figure 6 presents a schematic view of some specifications of interest in the 50G-PON recommendation edited by ITU-T in 2021 and 2023 [25]. In 2021, specifications for 25 Gbit/s US physical layer were available for Class N1 and C+, and more recently 50 Gbit/s US for Class N1 specifications were published. The highest optical (>29 dB) are still difficult to reach with 50G-PON prototypes and the use of optical amplification might be required in future evolutions.

Figure 6: 50G-PON scheme showing main specifications of interest

50G-PON is positioned as the primary successor to both XGS-PON and G-PON for higher speed PONs [26]. At first, 50G-PON predicted only double coexistence of PON technologies with the following wavelength plan proposing different US options: US1: 1270 +/- 10 nm; US2: 1300 +/- 10 nm; or US1 narrow: 1300 +/- 2 nm). However, these US options overlap either with the wavelength used by G-PON (1310 +/- 10 nm) or XGS-PON (1270 +/- 10 nm).

To deploy 50G-PON while maintaining XGS-PON on the same ODN, operators would need to remove all G-PON ONUs already deployed on their networks. Alternatively, 50G-PON could coexist with G-PON if no XGS-PON is present on the ODN, but this scenario is less desirable as XGS-PON has already been deployed extensively. Currently, the average selling prices of G-PON ONUs are four times lower than those of XGS-PON, and it is projected that by 2027, the price difference will still be at least twice as high [21]. Moreover, substantial volumes of 50G-PON are not expected within that timeframe, indicating that G-PON and XGS-PON will continue to be prevalent in FTTH networks for a considerable period.

Therefore, operators may find it more beneficial to pursue a smooth migration towards higher speed PONs, seizing the opportunity to deploy a few 50G-PON systems for specific demanding use cases. Besides economic considerations, operators face expectations to reduce their energy and environmental footprints, which involves minimizing power consumption, carbon emissions, and extending the lifecycle of network technologies [27]. Given the PON architecture, the impact of the OLT MPM transceiver is relatively limited compared to the numerous connected ONUs (fiber gateways). Consequently, preserving the lifecycle of existing ONUs while introducing new generations of optical gateways is crucial. Hence, replacing current G-PON or XG(S)-PON technologies with 50G-PON is not aligned with the initiatives to ensure sustainable networks for the next decade.

Hence, enabling triple coexistence of PON technologies becomes crucial. In a technical study proposed in [28], it was demonstrated that, for a small sample of 4180 field G-PON ONUs, the distribution of US wavelengths is limited to the upper band above 1305 nm. This study suggests a new wavelength plan that allows for triple coexistence by defining the acceptable range for the 50G-PON US wavelength within the window of 1290 nm to 1305 nm. However, there is a tradeoff to be determined to achieve an affordable range for the 50G-PON US wavelength. When considering Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) technologies, it is worth noting that Thermo-Electric Cooler (TEC)-free sources are only available for Coarse-WDM transceivers, and narrower spectral ranges require the use of temperature controllers. Therefore, finding a suitable tradeoff within this spectral window is still necessary to enable cost-effective triple coexistence of PON technologies.

In more recent developments, the ITU-T has recently approved the adoption of a new spectral band in 2023. This band, specifically at 1286 +/- 2 nm, allows for triple coexistence and does not overlap with any other PON technologies, including wide, narrow, and reduced bands. This spectral band aligns with one of the bands proposed in the IEEE standard for 25G-EPON, offering the potential for significant production volume. However, there are certain considerations with this narrow band. To ensure the laser emission stays within a 4 nm range, temperature controllers would need to be implemented at the ONU. Additionally, as this band is located close to the edge of XGS-PON filters, there is a risk of crosstalk with XGS-PON if the filters are not sufficiently sharp. To address this potential issue, OOB channel specifications were defined for this US channel option. By implementing these specifications, the triple coexistence of G-PON, XGS-PON, and 50G-PON

becomes possible on the same ODN, provided they all meet the same optical budget conditions.

As a result, discussions are currently underway regarding MPM configurations that support the triple technologies (refer to Figure 7) and CEx for the triple coexistence scenario (refer to Figure 8). These discussions aim to establish upcoming specifications and guidelines for these technologies.

In the end, triple coexistence of G-PON, XGS-PON and 50G-PON is now possible on the same ODN, given that they all support the same optical budget conditions. MPM with triple technologies (see figure 7) as well as CEx for triple coexistence (Figure 8) are then being discussed for upcoming specifications.

Figure 7: Proposed MPM scheme considered for triple coexistence of G-PON, XGS-PON and 50G-PON

The integration of MPM technology into Small Form Factor Pluggable (x-SFP) transceivers may present challenges due to space constraints and limitations in heat dissipation. This could potentially lead to a reduction in the number of PON ports per OLT card. Additionally, the adoption of MPM with triple coexistence would require operators to invest once again in already deployed interfaces for G-PON and XGS-PON, adding an additional cost burden.

Figure 8: CEx scheme considered for triple coexistence of G-PON, XGS-PON and 50G-PON

Implementing triple coexistence based on CEx offers a compelling option for a seamless migration towards 50G-PON. This approach allows operators to retain their current G-PON and XGS-PON MPMs and OLT cards while investing in dedicated 50G-PON ports and OLTs. However, this solution introduces additional losses in the ODN, which are estimated to remain below 1 dB.

Nonetheless, operators will need to allocate space and resources within their central offices to integrate this new passive device into each ODN that is to be equipped with 50G-PON.

Furthermore, the use of splitters in PONs leads to a specific challenge in terms of optical budget, particularly for the initial prototypes of 50G-PON. Recent advancements have demonstrated that the incorporation of specialized DSP and/or optical amplification can achieve optical budgets exceeding 32 dB at 50 Gbit/s [29]. However, the

selection of optical components and their limitations in terms of frequency bandwidth prove to be crucial factors in overcoming constraints on DSP and optical amplification. Introducing these elements into PONs for the first time comes with notable consequences, including additional costs and increased power consumption. Moreover, it necessitates the establishment of new metrics, such as Transmitter Eye Closure (TEC) and Transmitter and Dispersion Eye Closure (TDEC) and Optical Modulation Amplitude (OMA), in the 50G-PON standard, which can be complex to implement in field and certification assessments [30,31]. Furthermore, the use of optical amplification poses a higher risk of OOB crosstalk due to elevated levels of Amplified Spontaneous Emission (ASE) transmission.

Figure 9: Experimental setup of a 50G-PON system prototype assessment, considering coexistence with XGS-PON

We propose in this paragraph to detail our assessment of a first version of a 50G-PON prototype with one OLT equipped with QSFP28 50G-PON OLT module which is connected via a regular PON ODN to a 50G-PON ONU. The OLT and ONU transmit with a peak wavelength centered at 1342.7 nm and 1298.7 nm respectively. Figure 9 depicts the experimental setup used for this assessment. An Ethernet tester was used to qualify the link transmission of with 10 Geth packets of frame length or 1500 bytes in each direction (DS and DS).

Figure 10: Measured Eye Diagrams of DS and US signals at 50G-PON OLT and ONU respectively

Figure 10 presents the optical eye diagrams measured at the output the OLT (DS signal) at a clock rate of 49.766 Gbit/s and at the output of the ONU (US signal) at a clock rate of 24.88 Gbit/s. For the DS transmission the use of Digital Signal Processing is recommended, and we estimated the TEC of the DS transmitter to 2.95 dB and TDEC at 4.4 dB after 20 km transmission. The TDEC measurement requires to filter the signal offline and then to equalize it to emulate a limited bandwidth photodiode followed by a Finite Impulse Response filter, while the signal binary sequence is supposed to be a Short Stressed Pattern Random (SSPR) pattern as in indicated in G.984.3 ITU-T document [2]. However, emitting such sequence is not practically feasible when it comes to a system or prototype. Also, the equalization algorithm (not defined in ITU-T G9804.3 recommendation [2]) must operate without knowledge of the channel response, avoiding the use of the zero forcing algorithm. Thus, we used a blind equalization algorithm deriving from the famous Least Mean Square algorithm, as described in [32,33]. TEC and TDEC are calculated from a sample of 1500 bits (30 ns) length at 200 GS/s, averaged over 20 samples.

Figure 11: Packet Error Rate and LOS Alarm variation measured according to the optical budget available in DS and US, without XGS-PON being present (no CEx)

Figure 11 presents the Packet Error Rate variation measured according to the optical budget for the DS and US 50G-PON transmission without XGS-PON being present. We observed that the DS can reach a Packet Error Rate (PER) limit below 1.10^{-6} (corresponding to a BER below 1.10^{-9} for this frame length) for a received power of -19 dBm. This corresponds to an optical budget of 23.7 dB considering that we measured the output power at the OLT module at 4.7 dBm. For the US results, at $PER < 10^{-6}$, the OLT sensitivity is measured at -21 dBm which corresponds to an optical budget of 26.9 dB, the output power launched at the OLT being measured at 5.9 dBm.

These results are below standard specifications and could be enhanced by implementing more efficient DSP for the DS transmission and integrating better receivers at OLT for the US transmission. Also, introducing optical amplification based on SOAs as booster or pre-amplifier at OLT could be considered [34].

To achieve the highest optical budget, the optical power launched into the fiber from the 50G-PON OLT can be increased to up to 14 dBm according to standard specifications. The spectral spacing between the downstream and upstream options in 50G-PON is approximately 13 THz, which further amplifies the risk of Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS) [35]. Raman interactions between 50G-PON DS and US, and also between 50G-PON DS and XGS-PON US were pointed out in [36], leading to a maximum power depletion of 0.7 dB according to launched powers in both way and fiber length.

We propose here to extend this study with a commercial XGS-PON system and the 50G-PON prototype to verify SRS in the case of realistic PON implementation, with US burst mode transmission. Figure 12 presents the measured power variation on the US XGS-PON signal which is transmitted over the same ODN as the 50G-PON, using a CEx filter based on CWDM filters for wavelength overlay over a single ODN composed of 20 km of SMF and a VOA, as depicted in Figure 9. The US power is monitored with a burst mode PON power meter placed after a tap splitter at the CO and a CWDM filter centered at 1271 nm to drop the US 50G-PON signal and possible DS reflections.

Figure 12: Power depletion measurement due to SRS between 50G-PON DS and XGS-PON US with 20 km of SMF (G. 652.D type)

The power depletion plotted in Figure 12 corresponds to the difference between the US XGS-PON power measured without the DS and with the DS being injected in the SMF. The US power injected in the SMF was fixed at -0.5 dBm. After transmission in 20 km of SMF, the US signal power is decreased by 0.1 dB when the DS injected signal is the strongest (here +6.4 dBm). Similarly, after 10 km of SMF, a power depletion of 0.05 dB is measured on the US XGS-PON signal. Also, changing the burst duration from 50 % of the duty cycle to 100 %, in the case of 20 km transmission didn't change the results. The power depletion is observed with high repeatability and remains quite negligible (< 0.1 dB) and may not create significant trouble in the XGS-PON deployed which often have 1 dB margin of extra optical budget.

Finally, we present a smooth evolution architecture of G-PON, XG(S)-PON and 50G-PON, which uses 50G-PON & XG(S)-PON & G-PON combo line card and MPM (Figure 7) instead of 50G-PON optical module, XG(S)-PON optical module, G-PON optical module and CEx (Figure 13). In this architecture, G-PONs, XG(S)-PON, and 50G-PON users can exist in the same existing ODN. The number of 2/3 line cards and equipment room space can be saved. However, many challenges need to be overcome. For example, small-size Pluggable optical module support 16-port density per slot, high-power transmitters and high-sensitivity receivers compliant to support 29 dB and 32 dB power budgets, crosstalk between XG(S)-PON /G-PON and 50G-PON caused by narrow upstream wavelength isolation bands, and high module power consumption, etc.

Figure 13: Smooth Evolution Architecture of G-PON, XG(S)-PON, and 50G-PON

The above problems depend on the maturity of the 50G-PON industry chain which is still under progress. It is estimated that the components supply chain of 50G-PON will be ready in the year 2024, and 50G-PON may be ready for commercial use in 2025. Before the real deployment of 50G-PON, XG(S)-PON will be massively deployed in worldwide.

6. Conclusions

The paper presents the viewpoint of an operator regarding the current and future developments of Point-to-Point (PtP) and Passive Optical Networks (PONs) technologies and their co-existence.

This paper begins by emphasizing the importance of Next Generation Central Offices (NGCO) in facilitating the coexistence of PtP and PON topologies with the key network equipment being the OLT. We discuss how the OLT is the point of coexistence of FTTx technologies, an example being with today's deployment of FTTA (5G) and FTTH (G-PON and XGS-PON).

Also, we discuss about the possible future evolution of the OLT with regards to hardware evolutions including more and more photonics, and possibly express path, following trends developed in IOWN global forum and EU project OCTAPUS. Finally, we also address some of the motivations for OLT softwerization, regarding the evolution of the management layer, enabling cooperative configurations, hardware disaggregation and PON slicing.

Regarding PtP technology, the paper suggests that the PtP market could benefit from reducing the number of available solutions, particularly through the Mobile Optical Pluggable Alliance (MOPA) initiative. This initiative aims to simplify PtP deployments by offering standardized solutions from a reduced catalog of possible pluggable modules. Additionally, the paper proposes improvements in PtP technology with the arrival of 100 Gbit/s bidirectional transceivers in standards and in the market.

Concerning the co-existence of PON technologies, the paper identifies challenges related to Out-of-Band (OOB) issues, Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS), spectral and optical budget specifications, and interoperability. These challenges need to be addressed to ensure smooth coexistence and interoperability of different PON technologies.

Furthermore, this paper presents an experimental evaluation of a 50G-PON prototype system. Additionally, the paper measures the potential impact of Stimulated Raman Scattering (SRS) due to the coexistence of 50G-PON with XGS-PON. The experimental assessment highlights on the key role of the OLT for coexistence and the challenges the reach high optical budget required for the triple coexistence of PONs.

Funding Information. OCTAPUS HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-06 project (number: 101070009)

Acknowledgment This work was carried out in OCTAPUS HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-06 project (number: 101070009) and MARSAL H2020-ICT-52 project.

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